

Gravity, Electric Charge and Magnetism are results of Spacetime Curvature

(Unification of Gravitation with Electromagnetism)

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Abstract: Gravity, electric charge, and magnetism are all results of spacetime curvature. Each property can be defined as a result of the type of spacetime curvature through contraction, expansion, intensity, and state of these curvatures, defining properties previously considered distinct. Protons generate spacetime curvature of contraction, and electrons generate spacetime curvature of expansion, generated by extremely high, perfectly symmetrical pulsating vibrations. Gauss's equation needs to be adjusted to be applicable under conditions of large proportions of distributed charge in a massive body. In an atom, the electron exhibits changes in intensity when coupled to the nucleus, and the nucleus controls all states of the atom. The reception and emission of photons by electrons are also controlled by the atomic nucleus. These photons are responsible for canceling the electron's space-time curvature (electrostatic shielding) for varying amounts of time, and it depends on the energy of the photon received, which generates changes in the nucleus and in the state of the atom as a whole.

Text

Electric charges have been interpreted as an intrinsic property of the proton and electron particles. This analysis provides an understanding of the behavior of protons and electrons. In this analysis, electric charge is a result of the state of spacetime curvature, the curvature of space generated by the proton and electron particles, and depends on how the mass of each particle is distributed within the space they comprise.

The proton can have a spherical shape of extremely high density, generating a different type of spacetime curvature than the electron. The proton generates a spacetime curvature of concentration, that is, it generates a curvature of shrinking space around it, similar to gravity, but with much greater intensity.

The electron, in turn, generates a spacetime curvature of widening space, that is, the space around the electron becomes larger, a type of curvature opposite to that of the proton. This behavior is generated by the electron experiencing a state of pulsating vibration at a very high frequency. Its volume increases and decreases in size at a certain amplitude, generating the curvature of spacetime. The amplitude of this vibration is responsible for the electron's electric charge. Since the electron is a perfectly symmetrically pulsating particle (pure radial mode), it does not generate electromagnetic waves because the charge is always distributed uniformly around the center, only changing in size but without shifting the "center of mass." Thus, there is no energy loss due to this aspect.

The proton and electron, in their free state, have the same electric charge (maximum curvature of spacetime for particles), and they have virtually the same volume. However, the proton has a mass approximately 1837 times greater than the electron. This demonstrates that it is not only the value of mass that determines the curvature of spacetime, but also how this mass is distributed in space, as proposed for black holes. The estimated density near a proton is around 10^{18} kg/m³, and the estimated density of an electron is around 10^{14} kg/m³. They have a density close to that of a black hole, which is around 10^{19} kg/m³. This density similarity gives rise to a singularity for protons and electrons. This behavior is very different from that observed for an extended body.

Thus, the curvature of spacetime generated by an extended electrically charged body can be much greater compared to the curvature due to gravity. This significant difference in values may have influenced interpretations and led to the assumption that these are distinct properties.

The spacetime curvatures generated by proton-proton interactions do not couple and thus repel each other when these particles are placed close together. Electron-electron interactions behave similarly. However, particles like protons and electrons attract each other because the types of spacetime curvature couple to cancel each other out. Neutral particles exhibit a very small resulting intensity from the spacetime curvature; the result is considered gravity, as do electrically neutral atoms (the same number of protons and electrons).

Gravity is the result of the sum of the spacetime curvature generated by the effects of nucleotides. A kilogram of any material will have the same number of nucleotides. Therefore, gravity is the effect resulting from the protons of the atoms that make up any material. The sum of the proton and electron effects does not cancel out the total effect of the curvature generated by the protons, only the electrons. Thus, each proton and electron form a nucleotide, whereas neutrons naturally form a nucleotide. Gravity was analyzed as the curvature generated by the mass of the material, but this was only possible because the number of nucleotides in each material is the same. The mass of 1 kg of a given substance is on the order of $6 \cdot 10^{26}$ nucleons. Different substances have the same order of nucleons. This is because the mass of 1 kg is determined by the mass of the nucleons and not by the number of atoms.

Magnetism is a result of the behavior of electrons, as electrons generate a curvature of spacetime, this reasonably organized movement of electrons from the origin to the magnetic field.

Modified Gauss equation:

With the considerations presented, the Gauss equation now has the following behavior

$$\oint \vec{C} \cdot d\vec{A} = n\gamma + \beta M$$

where \vec{C} is the field generated by the curvature of spacetime. Being $n = n_p - n_e$, n_p is the number of protons and n_e is the number of electrons, for a neutral body $n_p = n_e$, therefore $n=0$; $\gamma = \frac{e}{\epsilon_0}$, where e is the elementary electric charge and ϵ_0 is the electric permittivity; $\beta = 4\pi G$ where G is the universal gravitational constant and M is the mass of the charged body.

The second term presents the following considerations:

- The two terms $n\gamma + \beta M$ will be significant together only under conditions of large charges and bodies with large masses.
- The βM term can be negligible in cases of small masses and charges. In this condition, only the $n\gamma$ term is relevant, the other becomes negligible.
- For small values of charge (n) and large masses, $n\gamma$ tends to zero, leaving only the βM term.

For this reason, no flaws have been observed in the Gauss equation. For this, conditions of large electrical charges distributed over a large mass, on the order of 10^6 kg, would have to be analyzed to observe their effects and the flaws in the Gauss equation.

Atom

In an atom, the nucleus creates a curvature of spacetime around it. Positive charges are responsible for this curvature, and the neutron contributes only slightly to this effect. The atom is the result of nucleus-electron coupling.

The electron is not a simple particle; it exhibits levels of spacetime curvature (electric charge levels, which change depending on the conditions, changing values) and depends on the configuration found in a given shell of an atom.

As the electron approaches the atomic nucleus (inner shells), it releases energy in a quantized form (photons), and the state of the atom changes. The protons in the nucleus generated a pronounced spacetime curvature. When the electron enters inner shells, it causes a new coupling. The spacetime curvature is reduced. With this new configuration, the protons expand (increase in size) and exhibit less spacetime curvature, that is, a lower electric charge. The larger the volume of a proton, the smaller the spacetime curvature it produces. The same happens with electrons: they begin to vibrate at a lower amplitude, generating a smaller curvature of spacetime or a smaller electric charge. This is because the electron's charge is determined by its vibration amplitude. The smaller the vibration amplitude, the smaller the curvature of the expanding spacetime.

Electrons exhibit different vibrational states (variable electric charge) for each coupling (bonding layer in the atom). Electrons in each innermost layer of atoms exhibit higher vibrational states, but with lower amplitude. The lower the vibration amplitude, the smaller the curvature of spacetime, and consequently, the smaller the particle's volume.

In the ground state, the electron exhibits a lower vibrational amplitude. Beyond this limit, if it approaches the nucleus, it begins to behave like a proton experiencing repulsion. This explains why electrons do not fall into the nucleus spontaneously. Each energy level is the limit for that group of electrons. The photon needs to have the frequency necessary to interact with the electron's vibrational state at the level it is in for energy level decoupling to occur.

This changes the curvature of spacetime generated by the nucleus, causing the electron to shift layers. The electron doesn't jump from one layer to another; it's the curvature of space that changes, causing the electron to shift into another layer, appearing to have made a leap; space has changed. When this happens, the atom changes as a whole. At this moment, the

protons in the nucleus decrease in size, increasing the curvature of spacetime. The nucleus will generate a new coupling of electrons to inner layers, seeking stability.

Therefore, for an electron, the closer it is to the nucleus, the higher the vibration frequencies and the lower the vibration amplitudes. The spacetime curvature decreases drastically, thus this curvature is linked to the vibration amplitude, not the vibration frequency. Another aspect is that as the electron gets closer to the nucleus, it shrinks in size. The opposite occurs with protons. When they couple with electrons, the spacetime curvature of the nucleus decreases, increasing the protons' volume.

The electron in a coupled state moves within the curvature generated by the nucleus, without losing energy. In the electron's frame of reference, it moves in a straight line, not a circle or any other motion. This behavior was proposed for planets orbiting the Sun by Albert Einstein's general relativity.

The vibration frequencies of electrons are high, so some photons can only interact with the electron due to their motion within an atom through the relativistic Doppler effect. A photon capable of causing an electron to change shells may have:

- Lower frequencies can partially cancel out the electron's space-time curvature (creating electrostatic shielding), causing the nucleus to change state, which in turn changes the nucleus's space-time curvature. When the electron returns to its new vibrational state, it is already in a different layer.
- Frequencies lower than the electron's vibrational state can only access the electron through the Doppler effect, which causes the partial cancellation of the space-time curvature for a time, a kind of electrostatic shielding, causing the nucleus to change the dimensions of space and shift the specific electron to a different layer.
- The Doppler effect allows electrons to jump to different levels of the photons they receive, resulting in a quantum jump (nuclear decoupling). This would explain why, above a given value, a direct jump with different frequencies (energies) to different layers is possible.
- The higher the photon's energy, the deeper the electron's spatial curvature can reach, and consequently, the longer the time for the electron's spatial changes to cancel each other out. The greater the electron's decoupling from the nucleus, the more it can reach more extreme layers (longer electrostatic shielding time).
- Frequencies above the cutoff frequency that can cause an electron to shift from one layer to another, only at specific frequencies, are controlled by the nucleus. These frequencies are the states of the nucleus that control the electrons. Thus, when a photon interacts with an electron, if it possesses the characteristics of a frequency above the minimum, the nucleus cannot stabilize in the new state. Because it lacks the energy level of the atom's reference layers, the nucleus causes instantaneous re-emission to the electron's previous state. However, the re-emitted photon is a new one; if the incoming and outgoing photons are identical, it is impossible to distinguish them.